

Final Report

1. General information

DFG reference number: Wi 2677/18-1, BE 6700/6-1

Project number: SPP 2299, Project 468589501

Project Title: “Frozen in Time: Ecology of paleo reefs“

Name of PIs: *Christian Wild (PI, UB) and Sonia Bejarano (PI, ZMT)*

Institute/Department:

Department of Marine Ecology, Faculty of Biology and Chemistry (FB2), University of Bremen, UFT, Leobener Str. 6, D-28359 Bremen

Leibniz Centre for Tropical Marine Research (ZMT), Fahrenheitstr. 6, D-28359 Bremen

Name of the cooperation partner: *Alessio Rovere (CaFoscari Uni Venice, Italy)*

Period covered by the report, overall funding period: 1.5.2022 – 31.7.2025

2. Summary

As global temperatures continue to rise, coral reefs face mounting pressure to adapt or collapse, making it essential to understand how these ecosystems respond to environmental change. The overarching aim of the Frozen in Time project was to compare, at multiple spatial resolutions, the Last Interglacial (LIG; 129,000–116,000 years ago) coral reefs of the southern Caribbean with their modern counterparts and to identify the factors and mechanisms driving any observed differences. This objective was accomplished through the integration of new paleoecological and modern field data, analytical techniques, and hydrodynamic modeling approaches. The project began with comprehensive field campaigns on Aruba, Bonaire, and Curaçao (the ABC Islands), whose coastlines are composed of fossilized LIG reef sequences frequently exposed by stream incision. Offshore, the living reefs, exhibiting varying degrees of degradation, provided opportunities to employ parallel survey methodologies on both fossil and modern systems. Across two major field trips, Structure-from-Motion/Multiview Stereo techniques (SfM/MVS) were applied to generate high-resolution digital twins from 47 fossil and 70 modern reefs. For fossil outcrops, lithology was documented, and well preserved coral colonies were sampled for corallite analysis. In modern reefs, SCUBA-based transect surveys produced comparable digital models alongside scaled close-ups of coral corallites. The second project phase focused on reconstructing these digital twins, developing machine-learning-based image segmentation workflows for outcrop and corallite analyses, and applying statistical analysis to the resulting ecological datasets. To investigate the physical mechanisms driving reef evolution, the project used both existing and newly generated atmospheric simulations from the TAPIOLA project (SPP 2299, Project No. 468688677) to drive nearshore hydrodynamic models for time slices at 127 ka, 124 ka, and the Pre-Industrial period. Results reveal significant spatial and temporal shifts in reef development across the ABC Islands during the LIG, strongly influenced by variations in prevailing wave regimes. Furthermore, the ongoing deterioration of modern reefs in this region—and globally—may constitute a stratigraphic marker of the Anthropocene (“golden spike”) in the geological record. All datasets and models produced during the Frozen in Time project have been released as open-access resources. These resources have contributed to the training and development of early-career researchers, including one BSc thesis and three MSc theses.

Zusammenfassung

Mit dem fortschreitenden Anstieg der globalen Temperaturen geraten Korallenriffe zunehmend unter Anpassungsdruck. Ein vertieftes Verständnis ihrer Reaktionsmechanismen auf Umweltveränderungen ist daher von zentraler Bedeutung. Das Projekt *Frozen in Time* hatte zum Ziel, Korallenriffe des Letzten Interglazials (LIG; 129.000–116.000 Jahre vor heute) im südlichen Karibikraum mit heutigen Riffen zu vergleichen und die Prozesse zu identifizieren, die Unterschiede in Struktur und Zusammensetzung verursachen. Grundlage bildete die Integration paläoökologischer und moderner Felddaten, analytischer Verfahren und Modellierungsansätze. Im Rahmen umfangreicher Feldkampagnen auf den ABC-Inseln (Aruba, Bonaire, Curaçao) wurden sowohl fossile als auch rezente Riffe untersucht. Die Küsten dieser Inseln bestehen aus fossilisierten Riffsequenzen des LIG, die häufig durch Erosionsprozesse freigelegt sind. Zeitgleich erlaubten unterschiedlich stark degradierte lebende Riffe den Einsatz vergleichbarer Erhebungsmethoden. Mithilfe von Structure-from-Motion- Multiview Stereo (SfM-MVS) Techniken wurden 3D-Modelle von 47 fossilen und 70 modernen Riffen erstellt. An fossilen Aufschlüssen erfolgten lithologische Beschreibungen und Probenahmen zur Korallit-Analyse, während in modernen Riffen transektbasierte, tauchgestützte Erhebungen vergleichbare digitale Modelle lieferten. Die zweite Projektphase konzentrierte sich auf die Rekonstruktion der digitalen Zwillinge, die Entwicklung maschineller Lernverfahren zur Bildsegmentierung sowie die Anwendung fortgeschrittener statistischer Verfahren zur Auswertung der ökologischen Datensätze. Zur Untersuchung der Steuermechanismen der Riffentwicklung wurden atmosphärische Simulationen aus dem TAPIOLA-Projekt (SPP 2299, Projektnummer 468688677) in gekoppelten hydrodynamischen Modellen für Zeitabschnitte bei 127 ka, 124 ka und der vorindustriellen Periode verwendet. Die Ergebnisse zeigen deutliche räumliche und zeitliche Variationen der Riffentwicklung über die ABC-Inseln hinweg während des LIG, beeinflusst durch Unterschiede in den Wellendynamik. Die anhaltende Degradation moderner Riffe könnte langfristig als stratigraphischer Marker des Anthropozäns („goldener Nagel“) im geologischen Befund dienen. Alle im Projekt *“Frozen in Time“* erzeugten Datensätze und Modelle sind als Open-Access-Ressourcen verfügbar und fließen in neue, von der EU, der Deutschen Forschungsgemeinschaft und weiteren europäischen Einrichtungen geförderte Forschungsinitiativen ein.

3. Progress Report

The overarching aim of *Frozen in Time* was to investigate whether the MIS 5e reefs in the ABC islands are different from their modern counterparts and then elucidate the potential drivers of these differences if present. The research was organized into four main objectives that structured the project's work program. In the following sections, we outline how each objective was addressed over the course of the project and present the corresponding results.

Numbers in bold within square brackets refer to items in the publication list on the previous page, while other references are cited in the footnotes.

3.1. Objectives

1. Determine which traits can be measured directly on both fossil corals within reef outcrops and their extant counterparts, compile the demonstrated connections between traits and coral functions, and estimate trait values per colony and species in both outcrops and modern reefs.
2. Quantify small- (intra-outcrop), medium- (across island), and large-scale (among-islands) spatial variability in the taxonomic structure of coral communities of fossil and submerged reefs, and infer how this relates to environmental variables.
3. Characterize the distribution of traits and trait values, and quantify the extent to which analogies and differences between modern and paleo coral traits can be identified.
4. Investigate whether the frequency distribution of trait values on the reefs varies in response to the environmental variables (e.g., light, wave, sediment input).

3.2 Generation of new field data to answer objectives

The *Frozen in Time* project achieved its primary objective through comprehensive fieldwork conducted across all three ABC Islands, as initially proposed. Given the scope of the research - encompassing surveys of both fossil and modern reef systems - two major field campaigns were carried out in the summers of 2022 and 2023. Both expeditions were coordinated by postdoctoral researcher Patrick Boyden.

The first campaign took place in Curaçao between May 3rd and July 7th, 2022. Its initial phase focused on developing a standardized workflow within the modern reef environment, followed by systematic surveys of twelve sites along the island's leeward coast. Between two and six photogrammetry surveys were completed per site, resulting in forty digital twins of modern reefs. Additionally, 58 coral colonies representing key reef-building taxa were photographed for scaled corallite imaging and digital reconstruction. This phase was supported by members of the core proposal team (Sonia Bejarano, Allesio Rovere, Yussuf El-Khaled), two master's students (Giulia Caporale and Aannabell Klinke), and collaborators from synergistic projects (Paolo Stocchi and Mark Vermeij).

The second phase, from June 17th to July 7th, 2022, focused on fossil reef exposures across ten sites (Figure 1). A total of 126 fossil coral samples were collected, along with 62 georeferenced photogrammetry surveys and detailed corallite documentation of 61 fossil colonies. Building on insights gained in Curaçao, the second field campaign was undertaken between May 15th and June 16, 2023. Fieldwork on Aruba (May 15th–31st) was followed by work on Bonaire (June 1st–16th). The Aruba team, comprising Patrick Boyden, Alessio Rovere, Giovanni Scicchitano, Denovan Chauveau, Giovanni Scardino, and Malena Dahm, operated in two sub-teams—one surveying modern reefs and the other fossil exposures. In total, they surveyed seven modern sites

(16 digital twins, 52 colonies) and eight fossil sites (21 digital twins, 192 colonies), collecting 65 fossil samples for U-Th series dating in Germany. Fieldwork concluded with a community outreach lecture by P. Boyden at the University of Aruba titled “Aruba and Corals: A Love Story.”

On Bonaire, modern reef work was additionally supported by Sonia Bejarano and a ZMT scientific diving team (M. Stuhr, S. Bröhl, and S. Schwerdt). Surveys covered 13 modern sites (26 digital twins, 182 colonies) and seven fossil sites (20 digital twins, 121 colonies). Altogether, 32 modern and 24 fossil sites were surveyed across the three islands, exceeding the initial objective of 20 combined sites.

Following field completion, extensive post-processing was undertaken to generate digital twins and scaled colony images. Master’s students Guilia Caporale and Malena Dahm, under Patrick Boyden’s and Christian Wild’s supervision, processed substantial portions of the dataset for their theses. All raw field data have been made openly accessible via Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/frozen-in-time/>).

Figure 1. Overview map of ABC Island Sites with offshore depth contours. Aruba sites: (1) Boca Urinama, (2) Boca Rancho Curason, (3) Boca Chikito, (4) Boca Blue Light, (5) boca 200 m southeast of Boca Chikito, (6) Dos Playa, (7) Rincon Beach, (8) Baby Beach/Roger’s Beach, (9) Rocky Beach, (10) Fuel Barge East, (11) Fuel Barge Northwest, (12) De Palm Island, (13) Renaissance Island, (14) Cruise Terminal. Curaçao sites: (14) Boka Kortalein, (16) Boka Patrick, (17) San Pedro, (18) Bock Labadera, (17) Boka Grandi, (19) Directors Bay, (20) Tugboat, (21) Carmabi, (22) Playa Daibooi, (23) Playa Porto Marie, (24) Casa Abou, (25) Playa Largo, (26) Playa Mansalina, (27) Playa Hundu, (28) Santa Martha, (29) Kana Chiki, (30) Playa Kalki. Bonaire sites: (31) Boka Slagbaai, (32) Boka Kokolishi, (33) Boka Chikitu, (34) Playa Grandi, (35) Boka Washikemba, (36) Vista Blue, (37) Alice in Wonderland, (38) Salt Beach, (39) Pink Beach, (40) Monte’s Divi Tree, (41) Andrea II, (42) Oil Slick, (43) Webber’s Joy, (44) 1000 Steps, (45) Bon Bini na Kas, (46) Boka Tolo, (47) Karpata, (48) King Willem Reserve. Fossil sites (red circles), Fossil and modern sites (teal squares), modern only sites (purple triangles). Original map is from Boyden et al., in prep (*Clim. Past*) [4]. Isobath, landmass, and basemap data are from Natural Earth.

3.3 Results related to objective 1: Trait comparability between fossil and modern corals

This next phase of the project proved to be the most elusive. As part of G. Caporale's master's thesis¹, a review of standardized morphological traits from the Coral Trait Database² (CTD; <https://coraltraits.org>) was conducted to identify which traits could be reliably recognized and quantified. In total, twelve colony-level traits and three corallite-level traits were selected for potential analysis. When these traits were applied to field data, a key limitation emerged: preservation bias (Figure 2a, e). Specifically, the degree of preservation in coral colonies and corallites strongly influences which morphological features can be measured and how accurately they reflect their original structures.

Figure 2. Examples of both modern and fossil colonies. **a)** Fossil *D. Strigosa* extracted from the digital twin of Boka Patrick, Curaçao. While the colony as a whole can be identified (outlined in yellow), information as to the actual extent is lacking. **b)** Example scaled close-up of the fossilized meandroid corallites of the same fossil *D. strigosa* colony in (a). Here the ridge of the corallite is well preserved while the remainder of the corallite is heavily eroded. **c)** Digital twin of modern *D. Strigosa* surveyed at Tugboat, Curaçao. **d)** Scaled close-up of modern meandroid corallites. **e)** Fossil *A. palmata* extracted from the digital twin of Boka Patrick, Curaçao (outlined in yellow). Only one side of the *A. palmata* colony is remaining preventing further quantitative analysis. **f)** Scaled close-up of tubular corallites of the *A. palmata* in (e). **g)** Digital twin of modern *A. palmata* at Tugboat, Curaçao. A portion of one branch is dead following infection by stony coral tissue loss disease. **h)** Example scaled close-up of modern tubular corallites of the same *A. palmata* colony in (g). Original figures modified from master thesis of Giulia Caporale, 2023¹.

¹ Giulia Caporale "Developing a non-destructive method to compare morphological traits between fossil and modern hard corals at Curaçao, Caribbean Sea." Thesis in the degree Master of Science Marine Biology. Faculty 2 - Biology/Chemistry, University of Bremen. 1st Supervisor: Prof. Dr. Christian Wild; 2nd Supervisor: Dr. Sonia Bejarano; Daily Supervisor: Dr. Patrick Boyden. 2023.

² Madin et al. "The Coral Trait Database, a curated database of trait information for coral species from the global oceans." *Scientific Data*, 3(1), (2016): 1–22.

Of the twelve colony-level traits assessed, only five including (1) Growth Form, (2) Typical Growth Form, (3) Coloniality, (4) Colony Outline Type, and (5) Polyp Density could be reliably identified. Three additional metrics, (6) Branch Length, (7) Branch Width, and (8) Maximum Colony Diameter, were quantifiable in branching colonies (Figure 2g); however, incomplete fossil exposure limited confidence in reconstructing full three-dimensional colony structures (Figure 2e).

At the polyp level, similar constraints were encountered. Of the four corallite-level traits available in the CTD, three were deemed suitable for analysis: (1) Corallite Diameter, (2) Longest Septum Length, and (3) Minimum Neighbor Distance. All three, however, were susceptible to degradation in the fossil record (Figure 2b, f). Both, G. Caporale and M. Dahm³, investigated these issues in their master's theses, demonstrating that while statistically significant differences exist between fossil and modern corallites across all three traits, the features being measured are not always equivalent; for instance, the distinction between the living polyp membrane and the corresponding fossil corallite boundary.

Addressing these limitations will require additional sampling of pristine corallite surfaces from both fossil and modern specimens. Such work will necessitate new field campaigns and permitting, extending beyond the present project's scope.

3.4 Results related to objectives 2 & 3: Spatial (and temporal) variability in fossil and modern coral communities

This phase of the project focused on quantifying the variability in the taxonomic structure of coral communities across modern and fossil reef systems at three spatial scales: intra-site, intra-island, and inter-island. Additional analytical workflows also allowed for examination of the temporal dimension of Last Interglacial (LIG) reef development. Statistical analyses were performed using generalized mixed-effects models and bootstrapping approaches to assess variability and significance.

The original plan was to compare both the taxonomic and functional structures of modern and fossil coral communities. However, early in the project it became clear that a direct comparison would not be feasible. Most accessible fossil reef exposures are situated along the windward (northeastern-facing) coasts of the ABC Islands, whereas modern coral assemblages are confined to the leeward (southwestern-facing) coasts (Figure 1). The contrast in hydrodynamic energy between these opposing coasts—driven by wave exposure—is the principal factor underlying this discrepancy. Consequently, the fossil reef analyses were divided into two primary manuscripts: Rovere et al., in prep. (to be submitted to *Earth's Future*) [3] and Boyden et al., in prep. (*Clim. Past*) [4]. The key outcomes of these analyses are summarized below.

On the leeward coasts, fossil reef outcrops were often inaccessible due to extensive urban development on the coastline. For instance, on Aruba, only one leeward fossil site (Roger's Beach; Figure 1, Site 8) could be surveyed. Reliable access to leeward fossil sequences was available primarily on Curaçao, enabling direct comparisons between fossil and modern reef communities. Using data from long-term photogrammetric quadrat monitoring that began in the 1970s (Figure 3d–e; Van Duyl, 1985⁴), we assessed coral community change over the past five decades alongside that of the LIG period.

The results show that, despite marked climatic fluctuations during the LIG (Figure 3a and b, Brocas et al., 2019, *Geophys. Res. Lett.*⁵; Brocas et al., 2016, *Earth Plan. Sci. Lett.*⁶) and higher relative sea level (Figure 3c; Chutcharavan & Dutton, 2021, *Earth Syst. Sci. Data*⁷; Muhs et al., 2012, *Quat.*

³ Malena Dahm, "Form follows function: transition of morphological traits in reef corals from the last interglacial to modern corals." Thesis in the degree Master of Science Marine Biology. Faculty 2 - Biology/Chemistry, University of Bremen. 1st Supervisor: Prof. Dr. Christian Wild; 2nd Supervisor: Dr. Sonia Bejarano; Daily Supervisor: Dr. Patrick Boyden. 2024.

⁴ Van Duyl, "Atlas of the Living Reefs of Curaçao and Bonaire (Netherlands Antilles)". Foundation for Scientific Research in Surinam and the Netherlands Antilles. 117 (1985).

⁵ Brocas et al., "Tropical Atlantic Cooling and Freshening in the Middle of the Last Interglacial From Coral Proxy Records". *Geophysical Research Letters*. 46, 8289–8299 (2019).

⁶ Brocas et al., "Last interglacial temperature seasonality reconstructed from tropical Atlantic corals." *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*. 449, 418–429 (2016).

⁷ Chutcharavan & Dutton, "A global compilation of U-series-dated fossil coral sea level indicators for the Last Interglacial period (Marine Isotope Stage 5e)". *Earth Syst. Sci. Data* 13, 3155–3178 (2021).

Res.⁸; Schellmann et al., 2004, J. Coast. Res.⁹; Rubio-Sandoval et al., 2021, Earth Syst. Sci. Data¹⁰; Dyer et al., 2021, PNAS¹¹), fossil coral cover exhibited only a minor, statistically insignificant decline in mid-LIG time, followed by recovery toward its end. Taxonomic composition varied through this interval, with the fast-growing *A. palmata* rising in dominance during mid-LIG (Figure 3g). This trend contrasts sharply with the progressive decline observed in modern shallow reefs (hard coral cover $\approx 30\%$ during LIG vs. $\approx 10\%$ by 2019¹²; Figure 3d–f), as well as with the current critically endangered status of *A. palmata* (Figure 3e). Because the modern reef decline correlates strongly with anthropogenic stressors, yet no analogous signal appears in the fossil record, these modern patterns likely represent a distinctly Anthropogenic signature in the geological archive [3].

Figure 3. Curaçao leeward fossil reef coverage in relation to Southern Caribbean climate during the Last Interglacial (LIG). **a)** Mean coral $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{seawater}}$ and **b)** mean coral Sr/Ca-SST anomaly for Bonaire corals (Brocas et al. 2019⁵; 2016⁶). **c)** Sea-level index points^{7–10} for the Northern part of the island of Curaçao with overlaying glacial isostatic adjustment (GIA) outputs for the island from Dyer et al. (2021)¹¹ where the solid blue line represents the best fit model. **d)** Changes in hard coral cover (%) and trends in hard coral cover loss (% year⁻¹) from 1973 to 2023 at 10m (solid) and 20m (dashed) depths on the shallow reefs of Curaçao. **e)** Time series of relative coral genus abundance (%) from 1973 to 2014 based on permanent quadrats at four sites and across four depths on the leeward coast of Curaçao (data from De Bakker et al.). **f)** Hard coral cover across the 6 sites on Curaçao surveyed and three stages of LIG reef growth indicated in (a–c). **g)** Community abundance at each stage of LIG reef growth, focusing on the main hard coral constituents of each stage. Modified after Rovere et al., in prep [3].

⁸ Muhs et al., “Sea-level history of past interglacial periods from uranium-series dating of corals, Curaçao, Leeward Antilles islands”. Quat. Res. 78,157–169(2012).

⁹ Schellmann et al., “ESR Dating of Coral Reef Terraces on Curaçao (Netherlands Antilles) with Estimates of Younger Pleistocene Sea Level Elevations.” J. Coast. Res. 204,947–957 (2004).

¹⁰ Rubio-Sandoval et al., “A review of last interglacial sea-level proxies in the western Atlantic and southwestern Caribbean, from Brazil to Honduras.” Earth Syst. Sci. Data 13,4819–4845 (2021).

¹¹ Dyer et al., “Sea-level trends across The Bahamas constrain peak last interglacial ice melt.” Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, 2021. 118 (33): p.e2026839118.

¹² De Bakker et al., “Long-term Shifts in Coral Communities On Shallow to Deep Reef Slopes of Curaçao and Bonaire: Are There Any Winners?” Frontiers in Marine Science 3, (2016).

Figure 4. ABC Island windward reef growth across the the LIG. a) Hard coral cover on each island. The solid line within each boxplot marks the mean observed coral cover, while the dashed line represents predicted values from island-specific GLMER models, confidence interval at 95%. **b)** Break down of main observed coral genera at each LIG stage. LIG stages correspond to those described in Figure 3. Modified from figures in Boyden et al., in prep [4].

On the windward coasts of the ABC Islands, fossil reef accessibility was greatly improved, allowing for a robust assessment of coral community variability across three spatial and temporal scales: intra-site, intra-island, and inter-island. Averaged across all three islands, hard coral cover remained stable through the mid-LIG at approximately 40 % (Figure 4). A significant decline occurred by the late LIG, however, with cover decreasing to below 25 % ($P < 0.001$; Figure 4a). At the inter-island scale, strong declines were detected on Aruba (-22.3 %, $P < 0.001$) and Curaçao (-15.7 %, $P < 0.02$) (Figure 4a). This late-LIG reduction in coral cover is attributed to falling relative sea level (Figure 3c).

Spatial patterns were also apparent in coral cover and community composition among islands and through successive stages of LIG reef growth. *Orbicella spp.* was the dominant taxon throughout most of the LIG across the three islands, except during the early LIG on Curaçao, where *A. palmata* contributed substantially to reef accretion (Figure 4b). Notably, statistically significant changes in coral genus composition occurred only on Curaçao ($P < 0.05$), characterized by a marked shift toward sub-massive colony morphologies (Figure 4b).

3.5 Results related to objective 4: Relationship between environmental variables and trait distribution

The final objective of this project was to extract environmental insights from the distribution of fossil coral traits. We combined corallite-scale data with the broader inter-island and intra-LIG datasets to assess spatial and temporal patterns. At the corallite scale, both corallite diameter and count differed significantly between islands. Samples collected in Aruba had smaller diameters and fewer corallites than those from Bonaire (diameter: $P < 0.001$; count: $P < 0.001$) or Curaçao (diameter: $P = 0.022$; count: $P = 0.004$). We attribute these variations primarily to island position within the Caribbean current system and nearshore bathymetry, as Aruba's more northerly location exposes it to stronger nearshore flow. However, additional factors such as turbidity or localized environmental variation cannot be excluded. Corallite metadata have been released open-access.

At the intra-outcrop and inter-island scale, our most significant results, presented in Boyden et al., in prep. [4], suggest substantial paleoenvironmental differences during the Last Interglacial (LIG). Modern coral growth is largely absent on the windward margins of the ABC Islands due to persistent trade winds and associated high wave energy. In contrast, during the LIG, extensive shallow fringing reefs developed and flourished (Figure 4), reflecting a period of elevated sea level. Field discussions consistently revisited why such robust reef sequences formed during the LIG [2], but not during the Holocene transgression¹³. Since other environmental factors (e.g., turbidity, sea surface temperature) should have influenced both sides of the islands similarly, we interpret the windward fossil reefs as evidence for markedly reduced hydrodynamic activity during the LIG.

To evaluate this hypothesis, we used southern Caribbean near-surface wind vectors from the CESM global circulation model (Scussolini et al., 2023, *Clim. Past*)¹⁴ at 127 ka to force a Delft3D Flow wave model. The simulations show a $>4 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ decrease in wind speed compared to pre-industrial conditions, corresponding to a 142% reduction in significant wave height (0.27 m vs. 1.58 m, respectively). For mid-LIG conditions (124 ka), a parallel analysis with the iCESM model conducted in collaboration with Dr. Ute Merkel and Donghao Li (MARUM, Uni Bremen, TAPIOLA project) produced a 50% reduction in wave height relative to pre-industrial values. All model input data, codes, and results have been released open-access.

Contributions to the Project

The main contribution to the project was made by Patrick Boyden, who worked as a postdoctoral researcher in the project, provided direct supervision of all student projects associated with the project, organized both field exercises, and obtained all permits. Principal Investigators and the main collaborator of the project (Sonia Bejarano, Christian Wild, Alessio Rovere) provided direction and support according to their respective expertise. Other colleagues who had a major role in the project were:

Prof. Dr. Mark Vermeji (CARMABI, Curaçao) - assistance with the part of the project involving activities in Curaçao.

Dr. Eric Mijts (University of Aruba) - assistance with the part of the project involving activities in Aruba.

Dr. Andreas Haas (NIOZ, the Netherlands) - collaboration on common era reef environments on Curaçao.

Dr. Benjamin Mueller (University of Bremen, Germany) - collaboration on common era reef environments on Curaçao.

Student assistants were involved to develop their own research projects that served as subjects for their respective master theses in the group of C. Wild, where Giulia Caporale contributed the initial coral trait compilation ("Developing a non-destructive method to compare morphological traits between fossil and modern hard corals at Curaçao, Caribbean Sea") and Malena Dahm investigated coral polyp morphology difference between fossil and modern reefs ("Form follows function: transition of morphological traits in reef corals from the last interglacial to modern corals"). Several

¹³ Focke. "Subsea (0-40 m) terraces and benches, windward off Curaçao, Netherlands Antilles." *Leidse Geologische Mededelingen* 51.1 (1978): 95-102.

¹⁴ Scussolini et al. "Modeled storm surge changes in a warmer world: the Last Interglacial." *Climate of the Past* 19.1 (2023): 141-157.

colleagues, listed as co-authors in the project publications, also contributed to the overall outcomes of the project according to their expertise.

Data management and availability of data

All data has been made available online on Zenodo and linked using digital object identifiers (DOI). Furthermore, all manuscripts are/will be published in peer-reviewed open access journals. All data derived from this project will therefore be findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR).

4. Published project results

Hereafter we report articles, data, and communications to conferences directly acknowledging the project. The names of project scientists and collaborators mentioned in the original proposal are underlined.

4.1 Articles in peer-reviewed journals (all Open Access)

1. Scardino, G., Rovere, A., Barile, C., Nandasena, N.A.K., Chauveau, D., Dahm, M., Boyden, P., Bejarano, S., Casella, E., Kelly, H., Mijts E. & Scicchitano G., 2025. Coastal boulders emplaced by extreme wave events impacting the ABC islands (Aruba, Bonaire, Curaçao; Leeward Antilles, Caribbean). *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 349, p.109136. DOI: 10.1016/j.quascirev.2024.109136

Submitted manuscripts (available on respective pre-print servers)

2. Chauveau, D., Boyden, P., Desfromont, F., Scardino, G., Scicchitano, G., Mijts, E., Bejarano, S., Dean, S., Cerrone, C. & Rovere, A., 2025. Unravelling the spatial variability of fossil coral reef morphology on Aruba and the implications for paleo sea level estimates. *Pre-Print - Under review in JGR - Earth Surface*, DOI: 10.22541/essoar.174060566.60651312/v1
3. Rovere, A., Boyden, P., Haas, A., Mueller, B., El-Khaled, Y.C., Bejarano, S., Wild, C., Mijts, E., Scicchitano, G., Scardino, G., Chauveau, D., Stocchi, P., & Vermeij, M., 2025. Unprecedented decline in modern coral reef communities could indicate the onset of the Anthropocene. *Pre-print*, DOI: 10.31223/X5414H.
4. Boyden, P., Li, D., Bejarano, S., Mueller, B., Wild, C., Mijts, E., Scicchitano, G., Scardino, G., Chauveau, D., El-Khaled, Y.C., Merkel, U., Stocchi, P., Vermeij, M., & Rovere, A., 2025. Paleocology indicates wave climate as key factor in coral reef development. *Pre-print*, DOI: 10.31223/X58Q9J.

4.2 Data

All associated data products are curated under the Zenodo community: <https://zenodo.org/communities/frozen-in-time/>.

1. Chauveau, D., Boyden, P., Desfromont, F., Scardino, G., Scicchitano, G., Mijts, E., Bejarano, S., Dean, S., Cerrone, C., & Rovere, A., 2025. Dataset from Chauveau et al. "Unravelling the spatial variability of fossil coral reef morphology on Aruba and the implications for paleo sea level estimates" [Data set]. Zenodo. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14899366.
2. Rovere, A., 2025. Supplementary data for: Unprecedented decline in modern coral reef communities could indicate the onset of the Anthropocene [Data set]. Zenodo. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15570498
3. Boyden, P., Bejarano, S., Mueller, B., Li, D., Wild, C., Merkel, U., Mijts, E., Scicchitano, G., Scardino, G., Chauveau, D., El-Khaled, Y. C., Stocchi, P., Vermeij, M., & Rovere, A., 2025. Electronic Supplementary Material for: "Paleocology indicates wave conditions as key factor in coral reef development" [Data set]. Zenodo. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15754719.
4. Boyden, P., Collection of modern hard coral scaled corallite images from the ABC Islands (Leeward Antilles, Caribbean) [Data set] Zenodo. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17465248.
5. Boyden, P., Collection of MIS 5e hard coral scaled corallite images from the ABC Islands (Leeward Antilles, Caribbean) [Data set] Zenodo. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17513234.
6. Boyden, P., Modern shallow reef orthomosaic dataset from the ABC Islands (Leeward Antilles, Caribbean) [Dataset] Zenodo. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17513294.

4.3 Presentations at conferences

Stocchi, P., Boyden, P., Rovere, A., Haas, A., El-Khaled, Y. C., Bejarano, S., Wild, C., Mijts, E., Scicchitano, G., & Vermeij, M.: Coral reefs of the Leeward Antilles (SouthernCaribbean) steered into unchartered waters by human impacts, EGU General Assembly 2025, Vienna, Austria, 27 Apr–2 May 2025, EGU25-21691, DOI: 10.5194/egusphere-egu25-21691, 2025.

Rovere, A., Bejarano, S., Boyden, P., Cerrone, C., Chauveau, D., Dean, S., Georgiou, N., Ryan, D. D., Rubio-Sandoval, K., and Wild, C.: The Last Interglacial (125 ka): clues to the future of a warming world and its coasts, EGU General Assembly 2025, Vienna, Austria, 27 Apr–2 May 2025, EGU25-12220, DOI: 10.5194/egusphere-egu25-12220, 2025.

Scardino, G., Barile, C., Nandasena, A. N., Lahbi, T., Muletto, E., Chauveau, D., Boyden, P., Bejarano, S., Rovere, A., Casella, E., Kelly, H., Mijts, E., & Scicchitano, G.: Coastal boulders related to extreme marine events impacting the ABC islands (Aruba, Bonaire, Curacao islands, Leeward Antilles), EGU General Assembly 2024, Vienna, Austria, 14–19 Apr 2024, EGU24-7834, DOI: 10.5194/egusphere-egu24-7834, 2024.